

FEATURES OF THE FACTOR STRUCTURE OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN WOMEN WHO UNDERWENT SURGERY FOR PELVIC PROLAPSE

Khamdamova M.T., Akramova D.E.

Bukhara Medical University named after Abu Ali Ibn Sina.

hamdamova.muhammad@bsmi.uz

Summary. In patients with pelvic floor muscle failure and combined cervical pathology, the quality of life before surgery was reduced due to impaired physical activity and sexual functioning; after surgery, all parameters returned to normal, indicating a favorable effect of organ-preserving transvaginal surgeries on the quality of life of patients.

Key words: pelvic organ prolapse, quality of life, gynecological surgery.

Relevance. The problem of surgical treatment of genital prolapse (GP) remains very relevant. The prevalence of prolapse in women is 11.4-41%, increasing with age and the risk of surgery for this disease (2.7-11%), [1,2]. The only effective method of treating GP and pelvic floor failure is surgery. Currently, over 300 methods of surgical correction of GP are known [1,40]. The goals of surgical treatment of GP are relief of symptoms, one-stage restoration of the normal anatomical position of the organs involved in prolapse, elimination of all disorders in the structure of the pelvic floor, restoration of the function of the pelvic organs. It is fundamentally important to use minimally invasive surgical interventions that give a minimal number of relapses [4,12,13,14,15,16,17]. As a rule, surgical correction of PG using own tissues is associated with a risk of relapse of up to 40% due to the failure of own tissues [1, 2,27,28,29,30]. Currently, many options for surgical correction of pelvic girdle syndrome using mesh implants have been proposed, which are conventionally divided by the type of access used (vaginal, abdominal, or a combination of vaginal and abdominal) and by the method of biomechanical fixation model - rigid fixation to the pelvic walls or restoration of the supporting structures of the pelvic floor [1, 2,31,32,33,34,35,36,37].

The modern surgical concept of pelvic floor plastic surgery is based on the "replacement" of damaged and defective pelvic fascia with a "new" one (creation of neofascia), which is pathogenetically justified and provides a reliable framework for the pelvic organs [3,4,18,19,20,21,22]. The conducted studies have shown the advantages of using synthetic polypropylene meshes, the efficiency of which reaches 81-95.8% [2,3,5,23,24,25,38,39,40]. However, the advantages and disadvantages of vaginal surgeries using synthetic implants remain a subject of discussion [1,3,25,26]. In 2011, the FDA decided to ban the introduction of new mesh implants for surgical treatment of PG due to the development of frequent complications when they are used without preliminary multicenter clinical trials. At the same time, in 2012, the FDA presented a report noting that the use of mesh implants in surgical treatment of prolapse in the world is still not decreasing. On the contrary, there is a tendency to increase the use of synthetic materials with a simultaneous decrease in the number of operations without the use of implants. Thus, the relevance of this study is due to the significant prevalence of prolapse, the inconsistency of data on the occurrence of prolapse and its recurrence, the insufficient effectiveness of various methods of surgical treatment, the high frequency of relapses, and dissatisfaction with the quality of life of patients after surgical treatment.

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The purpose of the study to increase the effectiveness of surgical treatment and improve the quality of life of women with genital prolapse.

Material and methods. A total of 475 patients who had undergone elective radical and organ-preserving gynecological surgeries were examined. Depending on the indications for surgical treatment, the patients were divided into 3 groups: Group I - 180 patients operated on for benign tumors of the uterus and ovaries; Group II - 123 patients with prolapse of the vaginal walls, pelvic floor muscle failure, elongation, hypertrophy, cicatricial deformation of the cervix; Group III - 172 women operated on for uterine prolapse.

A comprehensive examination was conducted, including generally accepted clinical and laboratory-instrumental research methods.

A modified questionnaire "Quality of Life of Women" was used to assess the quality of life of patients. The questionnaire consists of 7 sections: physical activity (1), sexual life (2), mental state (3), social activity (4), role functioning (5), self-assessment of health (6), self-assessment of quality of life (7). The physical activity of the patients was assessed by the following parameters: degree of fatigue, lethargy, drowsiness; state of vitality and physical strength, endurance; ability to perform significant physical activity. The following criteria were used to assess the sexual life of women before and after the operation: changes in sexual life; feeling of discomfort during sexual intercourse; avoidance of sexual relations; feeling of sexual dissatisfaction. The mental state was assessed by the following parameters: memory impairment; feeling of depression, sadness, anxiety or nervousness, feeling of emotional instability; decreased interest in upcoming events. The study of social functioning included an assessment of interpersonal contacts and social connections. This category considers: changes in relationships with relatives; relationships with friends; intolerance towards other people; desire to be alone. The quality of life category related to role functioning includes the following aspects: problems in work; rapid fatigue when running a household; changes in relationships with a spouse; relationships with children. The woman's self-assessment of her health was based on her own analysis of the quality of sleep; changes in urination function; the presence or absence of pain in the lower abdomen or lower back; bowel condition.

In each section of the questionnaire, the woman subjectively assesses her well-being according to various parameters depending on the intensity of manifestations from 0 to 5 points.

from 32 to 78 years old. Working women made up two thirds of those examined. A study of the somatic history showed that most of the women had previously suffered from various extragenital diseases. On average, each patient had 3.1 extragenital diseases in their history, of which in Group I - 3.01, in Group II - 2.5, in Group III - 3.5.

At the time of examination, 235 (49.5%) patients were postmenopausal. The average age of menopause was 49.6 ± 2.5 years. In Group I ($n=180$), in 78.9% of cases, indications for surgical treatment were combined pathology of the genitals (uterine myoma, adenomyosis, ovarian cysts and cystomas, ovarian endometriosis), in 21.1% - isolated pathology of the uterine body (uterine myoma, adenomyosis). The following surgical interventions were performed due to the identified pathology: amputation of the uterus with and without appendages (73–40.6%), extirpation of the uterus with and without appendages (107–59.6%).

Indications for surgery in Group II ($n=123$) were combined genital pathology (pelvic floor muscle failure, cervical pathology). All women in Group II were diagnosed with pelvic floor muscle failure, stage I genital prolapse according to POP-Q (41.5%), and stage II genital prolapse according to POP-Q (58.5%). Combined cervical pathology was diagnosed in 68 (55.3%) patients. The volume of

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surgeries in Group II was: Manchester operation in 68 (55.3%) women, anterior and posterior colporrhaphy with perineolevatorplasty in 55 (44.7%). Indications for surgical treatment in Group III (n=172) were: genital prolapse, pelvic floor muscle failure, in some cases combined with benign tumors of the uterus (62–36%) and ovaries (10–5.8%). The scope of surgery in all cases was transvaginal extirpation of the uterus with colpoperineolevatoroplasty, combined with unilateral and bilateral removal of appendages in 8 (4.7%) women and in 2 (1.2%) with bilateral removal of appendages.

All patients underwent measures according to modern generally accepted methods of postoperative management.

The following results were obtained in the study of the quality of life of women. Physical activity before surgery was reduced in all groups, the most pronounced disorders were in patients with uterine prolapse.

After undergoing organ-preserving transvaginal surgeries, the physical activity of patients normalized in all parameters. After radical transvaginal surgeries, physical activity significantly improved compared to the pre-surgery level, which is associated with the elimination of negative symptoms associated with uterine prolapse after surgery. After transabdominal hysterectomy, physical activity indicators did not reach the pre-surgery level, which indicates an unfavorable effect of radical transabdominal surgeries on women's physical activity and the insufficiency of the body's compensatory capabilities after surgery.

According to the parameter of sexual functioning before surgery, the greatest violations of sexual function were found in women with genital prolapse, the maximum degree of sexual dysfunction was diagnosed in patients with uterine prolapse.

In patients with benign tumors of the uterus and ovaries, sexual function before surgery was practically not impaired. After transvaginal extirpation, the level of sexual dysfunction progressively decreased - a year after the operation at the level of 1-2 points. After transabdominal hysterectomy, the indicators are at the level of "moderate degree" (3 points), which corresponds to the level before the operation.

Thus, both organ-preserving and radical operations performed by transvaginal access have a beneficial effect on sexual function in women, which is associated with the elimination of anatomical disorders caused by genital prolapse.

Before the operation, most women experienced neurotic disorders of an anxiety-depressive nature in response to the stress of the upcoming operation, which was manifested by increased values for the parameters "feeling of anxiety or nervousness", "decreased interest in upcoming events", "feeling of emotional instability". In the postoperative period, the indicators of urinary dysfunction in women after transvaginal operations progressively decreased, which indicates a positive effect of the operations on urinary function. In women, a year after transabdominal hysterectomies, the indicators of urinary system dysfunction changed insignificantly (1-2 points). Pain in the lower abdomen and lower back before surgery bothered women with benign tumors of the uterus and ovaries, uterine prolapse, after transvaginal radical surgeries gradually decreasing to 1-2 points, in the group of transabdominal radical surgeries the frequency of pain syndrome increased insignificantly to 2-3 points ($p > 0.05$). Problems with stool before surgery bothered women with uterine prolapse to a greater extent, the severity of manifestations was at the level of "insignificant" (2-3 points), after 12 months the indicators in all groups normalized.

Before surgery in Group I, only 21.6% of respondents rated their quality of life as good, in Group II - 52.0%, in Group III - 26.7% (Table 7). After surgery, 35% of women in Group I, 70.7% in Group II and 48.2% in Group III considered their quality of life to be good.

Conclusion. In women with benign tumors of the uterus and ovaries, the quality of life before surgery is reduced in terms of physical activity and mental functioning. After surgery, mental, role and social functioning worsened, which indicates an unfavorable effect of radical transabdominal operations on the quality of life of women, despite favorable long-term results of surgical treatment, which is the basis for developing a program of social and psychological adaptation and rehabilitation of women.

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